

ROLE OF HABITAT DEGRADATION AND FOOD WEB STRUCTURE IN THE PERFORMANCE OF WETLANDS AS CARBON SINKS

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project described in the file aims to ensure proper handling of the data produced during the research lifecycle. The DMP will follow the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to manage, archive, and make the data publicly available. The plan will be established early in the project to standardize procedures across partners, ensuring harmonization of metadata standards, quality control, and data preservation. The DMP also includes policies for data sharing and updates as needed throughout the project..

Funder

Ministero dell'Università e della
Ricerca (MUR)

Grant

MUR - BANDO 2022, Prot.
2022HRL2HL
(m_pi.AOODGRIC.REGISTRO_PR
IN2022.0005768.31-03-2022)

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Organizations

University of Salento, National Research Council of Italy– Institute for Agricultural and Forest Systems in Mediterranean, Sapienza University of Rome

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: **ROLE OF HABITAT DEGRADATION AND FOOD WEB STRUCTURE IN THE PERFORMANCE OF WETLANDS AS CARBON SINKS**

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University of Salento

National Research Council of Italy- Institute for Agricultural and Forest Systems in Mediterranean

Sapienza University of Rome

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR)

Grants: MUR - BANDO 2022, Prot. 2022HRL2HL

(m_pi.AOODGRIC.REGISTRO_PRIN2022.0005768.31-03-2022)

Project: [ROLE OF HABITAT DEGRADATION AND FOOD WEB STRUCTURE IN THE PERFORMANCE OF WETLANDS AS CARBON SINKS](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[PRIN- Data Management Plan_Version_1](#)

The context of the "Description of different data types" in the document refers to the management of data collected from various research activities, specifically focusing on wetlands and their ecosystem dynamics. The purpose is to ensure that all data types—such as carbon and nitrogen inputs, isotopic analysis, vegetation data, hydrological and satellite data, and food web structures—are clearly described, processed, and made interoperable for research and conservation purposes.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
MULLA Divya Pragna	0000-0002-3468-7061	divyapragna.mulla@unisalento.it	University of Salento
Alberto Basset	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3603-	alberto.basset@unis	University of

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1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
BASSET Alberto	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3603-9316	alberto.basset@unisalento.it	University Of Salento	Creator
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MULLA Divya Pragna	0000-0002-3468-7061	divyapragna.mulla@unisalento.it	Univeristy of Salento	Research Collaborator
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1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

- a. University of Salento
- b. Sapienza University of Rome
- c. National Research Council of Italy (CNR) - Water Research Institute (IRSA)

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

In the project, resources dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) are well-defined. These include both financial and time-related costs to ensure compliance with best practices for research data management. Based on the information provided in the project document:

Financial Resources:

The project allocates specific budget items for data management activities, including the use of standardized tools for data collection, processing, ingestion, and preservation. This is in line with the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal, which ensures that data is managed according to the FAIR principles.

Resources are dedicated to metadata generation and management, ensuring data is properly described using the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) and assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), which is essential for making data findable and accessible.

Time and Personnel Resources:

The project involves significant time investments from key personnel, including David Rossi and Maria Letizia Costantini, who contribute to data collection, stable isotope analysis, and food web reconstruction. The project tasks, such as data mining, meta-analysis, and isotopic analysis, are coordinated to ensure that all data remains accessible and interoperable.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed early in the project (within the first 3-6 months) and continuously updated, reflecting the harmonized standards and quality control procedures.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.1 Work package and task number

WP	Task
<p>WP4: Data Mining, Meta-Analysis, and Data Organization Tasks</p>	<p>Data mining from existing literature to calibrate field and lab experiments. Organize and manage all collected data following the FAIR principles. Structure data using the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal with associated metadata using Ecological Metadata Language (EML). Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) and maintain standardized procedures for data processing and sharing</p>

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

No

2.1.3 Creating a new dataset

A new dataset is being created as part of the current research project because existing datasets do not fully capture the specific phenomena this project is investigating. The project focuses on understanding the effects of habitat degradation and food web structure on the carbon sink capacity of wetlands, which requires unique experimental data from various locations (e.g., coastal lagoons and freshwater ponds) across different seasons.

Additionally:

Existing datasets may not provide data at the required spatial resolution or may lack specific measurements, such as stable isotope analysis of carbon and nitrogen or the detailed food web structures that this project aims to construct.

The project involves collecting new, site-specific data on carbon and nitrogen fluxes, vegetation cover, and hydrological changes in Italian wetlands, which might not be available in previous datasets.

Ethical or copyright restrictions may prevent the reuse of existing data, as some proprietary or unpublished datasets are not publicly accessible.

Thus, producing a new dataset is essential to meet the project's objectives and ensure the accuracy and relevance of the research

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

PRIN2022.WP1-5.Wetland_Ecosystem_Data.v1

2.2.2 Data types

- a. 1. Numerical Data: - Includes measurements such as carbon and nitrogen concentrations, CO₂ emission rates, hydrological parameters (e.g., water temperature, salinity), and decomposition rates. - Type: Quantitative, raw, and processed.
- b. 2. Textual Data: - Descriptive information on site conditions, vegetation cover, anthropogenic pressure, and sampling methods. - Type: Qualitative, textual.
- c. 3. Graphical Data: - Geographic Information System (GIS) maps, such as drainage patterns and vegetation cover generated from Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and satellite imagery (NDVI). - Type: Visual, processed.
- d. 4. Derived Data: - Data on food web structures, derived from isotopic analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) and reconstructed through modeling. - Type: Quantitative, derived.
- e. 5. Raw Data: - Field measurements of CO₂ emissions, sediment samples, vegetation biomass, and isotopic values. - Type: Raw, quantitative.
- f. 6. Processed Data: - Cleaned and aggregated datasets of carbon and nitrogen inputs/outputs, vegetation indices, and hydrological variables, ready for analysis.

2.2.3 Data formats

- a. 1. CSV (Comma-Separated Values): - For numerical data such as carbon and nitrogen concentrations, CO₂ emission rates, and other field measurements. - Use: Raw and processed quantitative data.
- b. 2. TXT (Text Files): - For textual data, including site descriptions, sampling notes, and metadata. - Use: Qualitative information.

- c. 3. GIS Formats (e.g., .shp, .geojson): - For graphical data such as GIS maps of drainage patterns, vegetation cover, and NDVI. - Use: Visual, spatial data.
- d. 4. XLSX (Excel Spreadsheet): - For organizing and analyzing data, including data summaries, derived calculations, and meta-analysis. - Use: Quantitative and processed data.
- e. 5. JPG/PNG (Image Files): - For graphical representations of data, such as satellite images, maps, or graphs. - Use: Visual data.
- f. 6. PDF (Portable Document Format): - For reports, data summaries, and documentation of methodologies. - Use: Processed qualitative and graphical data.

2.2.4 Size of data

gigabytes (GB)

Comment:

The dataset for this project is expected to fall within the 1 GB to 20 GB range. This estimation includes:

- Numerical data (e.g., CSV, XLSX files): Likely small in size but abundant in quantity due to repeated measurements over time and across multiple wetland sites.
- GIS and graphical data (e.g., .shp, .geojson, JPG/PNG): These files could contribute more significantly to the size due to high-resolution satellite imagery and detailed maps.
- Raw and processed data from fieldwork and lab experiments (e.g., isotopic analysis, CO₂ emissions, and decomposition rates), which may increase the overall size.

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The data for this project is collected and generated through a combination of field experiments, laboratory analyses, and remote sensing technologies. Here's an outline of the process:

1. Field Data Collection:

- Fieldwork will be conducted across three coastal lagoons and three freshwater ponds in Italy, focusing on various ecological parameters such as CO₂ emissions, carbon and nitrogen inputs/outputs, water quality, and vegetation biomass.
- Physicochemical parameters like temperature, salinity, pH, and conductivity are collected using multiparameter probes.
- Sediment samples are taken to analyze organic matter and carbon storage, while aquatic vegetation, invertebrates, and fish are sampled for stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$).

2. Remote Sensing and GIS Data:

- Satellite imagery (from Landsat and Sentinel satellites) is used to compute Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), providing data on vegetation cover and productivity.
- GIS mapping is conducted to track hydrological patterns, surface runoff, and anthropogenic pressures using Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Corine Land Cover (CLC) maps.

3. Laboratory Experiments:

- Isotopic analysis of collected samples (sediments, vegetation, and organisms) is conducted in the lab using mass spectrometry to determine carbon and nitrogen sources and food web structure.
- Decomposition rates of organic matter are measured through controlled litterbag experiments in both field and laboratory settings.

4. Data Provenance:

- The provenance of the data is carefully tracked by maintaining metadata for each dataset. Metadata follows the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) standard and includes information about data sources, collection methods, and any transformations or analyses applied to the raw data.

- Every dataset will be assigned a unique identifier (DOI), and data transformations (e.g., processing or cleaning steps) will be documented to ensure transparency throughout the data lifecycle.

5. Data Citation:

- Data generated will be made publicly available through the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, with proper citations for satellite data sources (e.g., USGS Landsat, Sentinel).

This systematic process ensures that all data collected in the project adheres to the FAIR principles and remains traceable, reproducible, and transparent throughout its lifecycle.

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The data is generated and collected to support the core objectives of the project, which is to understand how habitat degradation and food web structure influence the carbon sink capacity of wetlands. Specifically, the data will help achieve the following key goals:

1. Assessing the Carbon Sink Capacity of Wetlands:

- Data on carbon and nitrogen inputs/outputs, sediment composition, and organic matter decomposition are collected to quantify the ability of wetlands to store carbon and assess their role in mitigating climate change.

2. Investigating Food Web Structures:

- The project uses isotopic analysis to map food webs in wetland ecosystems, focusing on how interactions between species influence carbon cycling, organic matter decomposition, and overall ecosystem productivity.

3. Understanding the Impact of Anthropogenic Pressure:

- Data on water quality, land use patterns, and hydrological changes will help quantify the effects of human activities (e.g., pollution, agriculture) on wetland ecosystems and their functioning as carbon sinks.

4. Evaluating Habitat Conditions:

- Remote sensing and NDVI data will be used to track changes in vegetation cover and productivity in response to environmental stressors, contributing to wetland conservation strategies.

Future Uses of the Data:

- Inside the project scope:

- The data will be used to model the impact of climate change and anthropogenic pressures on carbon sequestration and emissions in wetlands.

- It will provide recommendations for wetland restoration and management, identifying appropriate targets and indicators for conservation efforts.

- Outside the project scope:

- The dataset will be made publicly available for further research through the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, enabling its use in other studies related to ecosystem services, biodiversity, and climate change mitigation.

- Policy makers, environmental agencies, and conservation groups can use the data to inform wetland management and contribute to international initiatives like the Ramsar Convention and the EU Water Framework Directive.

2.2.7 Dataset description

Dataset Abstract:

The dataset associated with the project "ROLE OF HABITAT DEGRADATION AND FOOD WEB STRUCTURE IN THE PERFORMANCE OF WETLANDS AS CARBON SINKS" provides comprehensive data on wetland ecosystems, focusing on how habitat degradation and alterations in food web structures influence their role as carbon sinks.

This dataset includes:

- Ecological and Environmental Data: Information on various wetland sites' physical, chemical, and biological conditions.
- Biomass and Species Diversity: Detailed records of species composition, biomass, and biodiversity across trophic levels, highlighting the effects of habitat degradation on these variables.
- Trophic Dynamics: Stable isotope analysis data used to reconstruct food webs, track nutrient transfers, and assess the impact of biodiversity changes on carbon cycling within wetlands.
- Hydrological Data: Models of water dynamics within wetland ecosystems, helping to evaluate the effects of water flow changes on carbon sequestration.

The dataset aims to offer insights into the interplay between wetland degradation, food web interactions, and their effectiveness as carbon sinks. It supports data-driven wetland restoration and management approaches, contributing to climate change mitigation efforts.

This dataset is intended for use by ecologists, environmental scientists, and policy-makers working on wetland conservation, climate action, and ecosystem sustainability.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.2.2 Legal issues: description and solutions

No major legal issues are expected concerning the output of this project. The dataset consists of ecological, hydrological, and biological data from wetland ecosystems and does not include personal or sensitive information. Therefore, the primary concern is ensuring compliance with open data and intellectual property rights under the chosen license.

-Ethics Committee Approval:

Ethics committee approval is not applicable since the dataset does not involve human subjects or personal data. However, in the case of any data involving fieldwork or protected wetland species, relevant permits and compliance with environmental regulations were obtained from the competent authorities prior to data collection.

-Strategies for Minimizing Ethical Issues:

a) Open Access and Licensing: All data will be shared openly under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY 4.0) license, allowing for widespread use and adaptation while requiring proper attribution to the data creators. This ensures that the data can be freely accessed and utilized by the scientific community and the public.

b) Controlled Access (if required): In cases where specific data might involve sensitive environmental locations or species at risk (e.g., endangered wetland habitats), access to certain sensitive datasets may be restricted. In such instances, controlled access mechanisms will be put in place to protect vulnerable ecosystems while ensuring that the data remains available to authorized users, such as researchers and policy-makers.

c) Long-Term Preservation and Data Integrity: All datasets will be stored in a trusted repository that follows standard protocols for data security, versioning, and long-term preservation. The repository will ensure that the data is accessible and reusable while maintaining the integrity and authenticity of the original dataset.

These measures will ensure that legal and ethical concerns are addressed effectively while maintaining the openness and accessibility of the research data for societal and scientific benefit.

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

1. Data to be Preserved:

Primary Research Data: All core datasets related to habitat degradation, food web structure, biomass, and carbon sequestration will be preserved in full. These include:

Ecological and environmental data on wetlands (e.g., biodiversity, species composition, carbon flow).

Hydrological models and data related to water dynamics within wetland systems.

Stable isotope data is used to reconstruct food webs and nutrient transfer within ecosystems.

Any associated field observations, measurements, and experimental data that contribute to the project's outcomes.

2. Data to be Discarded:

Intermediary Data: Temporary or intermediary data, such as raw files that are used during the process of data cleaning or manipulation but have no added scientific value once refined, may not need to be preserved long-term.

Replicable Data: Data that can be easily replicated (e.g., certain computational or derived models) may not need to be preserved, especially if the process of generating it is well-documented and replicable using the retained data.

3. Legal and Regulatory Considerations:

There are no specific contractual or regulatory requirements mandating the destruction of data. However, data that falls under environmental regulations, particularly those about sensitive ecosystems, may need to be preserved with controlled access.

No sensitive personal data is included in the dataset, so there are no legal obligations to delete or anonymize data based on privacy concerns.

4. Plan for Selection:

In cases where the dataset size becomes excessive or where parts of the data are easily replicable, a selection process will be applied. Priority will be given to retaining:

Data that is unique and non-replicable, such as field measurements and experimental results.

Data that is highly valuable for future research, policy-making, or ecological restoration efforts.

Final decisions on data preservation will be made with input from researchers to ensure the retention of the most relevant and impactful information for future use.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Dryad	https://datadryad.org/	Yes	Yes	Discipline specific
PANGAEA (Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science)	https://www.pangaea.de/	Yes	Yes	Discipline specific
Lifewatch	https://dataportal.lifewatchitaly.eu/data	Yes	Yes	Institutional

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
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not yet available	not yet available

4.2.2 Metadata

The metadata for the project’s research output will be generated and structured to ensure it adheres to recognized standards and facilitates data discovery, reuse, and long-term preservation.

Planned Metadata Strategy:

Metadata Standards:

The project will use the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) standard, a widely recognized metadata format for ecological and environmental datasets.

This ensures that the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) across various repositories and research platforms.

Content of Metadata:

The metadata will include the following key information:

Title: The name of the dataset, reflecting its content (e.g., "PRIN2022.WP1-5.Wetland_Ecosystem_Data").

Authors: The contributors and their affiliations, including roles such as data collectors, analysts, and PIs.

Description: A detailed abstract of the dataset, outlining the research context, objectives, data types, and collection methods.

Keywords/Tags: Specific keywords related to wetland ecosystems, carbon sequestration, food web structures, biodiversity, and climate change impacts.

Geospatial Information: Coordinates and descriptions of the locations of the wetlands studied (if applicable and not sensitive).

Temporal Coverage: The time period during which the data was collected (e.g., seasonal data across 2 years).

Provenance Information: Details on how the data was collected, processed, and transformed throughout its lifecycle.

Licensing and Access Information: Indicating if the data is open access or subject to specific licensing terms.

Data Format: File formats used (e.g., CSV, GIS, XLSX, etc.).

Repository Selection:

The dataset will be archived in the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal and LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, both of which support EML and ensure compliance with international metadata standards.

These repositories will assign a unique DOI to the dataset, further supporting data tracking and citation.

Metadata Creation and Updates:

Metadata will be created early during the data collection process and continuously updated as the dataset evolves.

The project team will ensure that any changes in data processing or structure are reflected in the metadata, maintaining its accuracy and relevance throughout the project.

This comprehensive metadata will enhance the discoverability and usability of the dataset by other researchers and stakeholders, ensuring proper documentation and alignment with FAIR principles

4.2.3 Keywords

Keywords that will be provided in the metadata to optimize discovery and reuse of the dataset include:

Wetlands, carbon sequestration, food webs, biodiversity, habitat degradation, anthropogenic pressure, nitrogen inputs, climate change, ecosystem services, hydrology, vegetation cover, coastal lagoons, freshwater ponds, stable isotopes, organic matter decomposition, carbon cycling, nutrient inputs, ecosystem functioning, remote sensing, GIS, NDVI.

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

No

4.3.2 Controlled access

The reasons for not making the research output openly accessible online are primarily related to data management protocols involving sensitive environmental data and ensuring compliance with relevant policies. Controlled access may be

needed to protect intellectual property, manage sensitive ecological data, or comply with legal frameworks governing environmental research, such as those ensuring the protection of wetland ecosystems or related policies mentioned in the document

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The research output can be accessed through the LifeWatch ITA Data Portal and LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, where all metadata and research data will be archived. If the data is not openly available, access can be granted upon request, and managed through controlled access mechanisms in compliance with the data management policies established. These strategies ensure that sensitive data is protected while still allowing authorized users to access the information through formal request processes.

If detailed information on access is not yet available, you can outline the plan to archive data in repositories such as LifeWatch ITA and indicate that a structured access request procedure will be implemented.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

The methodologies followed throughout the data lifecycle, as outlined in our project, include standardized procedures based on the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). These involve the collection, processing, ingestion, and preservation of data, using tools developed by LifeWatch to ensure that all research data is compliant with these principles.

Specifically:

1. Data Collection: Data is gathered in the field and laboratories using standardized techniques across various study areas. This involves collecting biological, chemical, and environmental data, such as carbon sequestration rates, vegetation coverage, and food web structures.

2. Data Processing: After collection, data is processed through calibrated models and analysis software to ensure quality control and consistency.

3. Ingestion and Preservation: Processed data is archived using the Data Schema of the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal, ensuring structured organization and accessibility.

4. Metadata: Metadata is associated with the data using the Ecological Metadata Language (EML 2.2.0), and a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is assigned to each dataset.

For data management, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed early in the project, which includes harmonized standards and quality control procedures.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

The methodologies that will be followed for vocabularies, taxonomies, and other standards include the use of standardized vocabularies and controlled terms relevant to the environmental and ecological fields. For metadata, the project will use the Ecological Metadata Language (EML 2.2.0), which is a well-established standard within the LifeWatch infrastructure. Additionally, taxonomies related to species and ecological classifications will likely follow structured systems to ensure consistency and interoperability. This standardization supports the FAIR data principles and ensures that the research outputs are accessible and reusable. If more specific vocabularies or ontologies are not yet determined, the plan will indicate that recognized standards will be used, such as those from ecological and biological research communities.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Comment:

The research output from your project will likely be licensed under Creative Commons licenses, such as CC BY 4.0 ("Attribution"), by the Horizon Europe guidelines. This license ensures that the data is shared with proper attribution to the authors, allowing for reuse and distribution.

4.5.2 Documentation

The documentation will be provided alongside the research output and will include comprehensive metadata, associated with data using the Ecological Metadata Language (EML 2.2.0), and any necessary readme files or codebooks for interpreting datasets. If specific software is required to access or analyze the data, references to the software will be included, and where possible, open-source software will be provided. The data and models will be structured using the Data Schema of the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal, ensuring the output is well-documented for future use and reusability

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

To ensure the quality and consistency of the research output, several measures will be implemented throughout the project. These might include:

1. **Standardized Data Collection:** Standard protocols for data collection will be followed to ensure accuracy and reliability. Field and lab experiments will be conducted in the wetlands using consistent methodologies.
2. **Calibration and Quality Control:** Calibration of experiments, such as carbon measurements, will be applied. Regular calibration of instruments will ensure the accuracy of data collected on parameters like carbon uptake and release.
3. **Repeated Sampling and Measurements:** To check for consistency, repeated sampling in different seasons will be conducted. This approach will allow the team to cross-verify data and detect any inconsistencies in environmental conditions and data trends.

4. Data Entry Validation: Quality control procedures will be established to ensure that data entry is accurate and free from errors. This could involve double-checking data entry points and validating datasets before ingestion into the repository.
5. Peer Review: All data and metadata will be peer-reviewed before final submission to ensure adherence to the project's data management plan.
6. Controlled Vocabularies: The use of controlled vocabularies (such as the Ecological Metadata Language (EML 2.2.0)) will ensure the standardization of terms and data descriptions, making the data more consistent and interoperable.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Institutional internal Server

Comment:

Below is an outline of the storage solution and access management:

1. Storage Solution:

a) Primary Storage:

- Data will be stored on institutional servers managed by the University of Salento and its partners (Sapienza University of Rome, CNR-IRSA). These servers offer high storage capacity and ensure the data is securely backed up during the research phase.

- Cloud storage may also be used to facilitate easy access and collaboration, especially for large datasets like GIS files or satellite imagery.

b) Backup:

- Automatic regular backups will be scheduled on redundant servers to prevent data loss.
- Data replication across ****multiple geographic locations**** will be implemented to ensure long-term preservation during the active research phase.

2. Access and Collaboration:

a) Access Control:

- Access to the data will be role-based, with different levels of permissions granted to researchers, collaborators, and data managers.
- Principal Investigators (PIs) and team leaders will have full administrative access, while other team members will have access limited to specific datasets or work packages.
- Collaborators outside the core team will be granted access through secure logins, with read-only or edit privileges as needed, depending on their role.

b) Tracking Access:

- Access logs will be maintained to track who accesses, modifies, or downloads the data. This ensures accountability and traceability of data use, especially in collaborative partnerships.
- Collaborative tools such as shared folders and version control systems will be used to track changes made to datasets during active research. This ensures transparency and prevents overwriting of critical data.

c) Security:

- Data access will be secured using multi-factor authentication (MFA) and encrypted connections to prevent unauthorized access during active phases of the project.

3. Future Plans:

- After the active research phase, the dataset will be transferred to long-term storage solutions like the LifeWatch Italy Data Portal, where it will be archived, indexed, and made available for reuse under controlled access conditions, ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles.

5.2.2 Backup

The project will implement a robust backup strategy to ensure data safety and recovery in case of an incident. Here's the outline of the backup approach:

Backup Strategy:

1. Regular Backups:

- Automatic daily backups of all data will be scheduled on institutional servers, ensuring that no data is lost during active research.

- A weekly full backup will be performed, with incremental backups happening daily to capture changes made to the datasets.

2. Redundant Storage Locations:

- Backups will be stored in multiple locations, including:

- Primary on-site servers at the University of Salento and partner institutions.

- Off-site cloud storage to provide an additional layer of security and disaster recovery.

- This redundancy ensures that in the event of server failure or physical damage, data can still be recovered from the remote backup.

3. Version Control:

- A version control system will be used to manage different versions of datasets. This will allow recovery of specific versions of data in case of accidental overwriting or deletion.

File and Folder Recovery:

- Recovery Procedures:

- In case of data loss or corruption, files and folders can be restored from the latest backup using the backup management interface provided by the storage solution.

- Recovery will be facilitated by the backup logs, which track all backup activities and identify the most recent stable version of any dataset.

- Time to Recovery:

- Files can typically be restored within 24 to 48 hours of an incident, depending on the size of the dataset and the nature of the issue.

- Immediate restoration can be performed from on-site backups for minor incidents, while off-site cloud backups will be used in the event of major incidents (e.g., hardware failure, cyberattacks).

Testing and Monitoring:

- The backup system will be regularly tested to ensure data can be recovered successfully.

- Alerts and notifications will be set up to monitor backup success or failure, ensuring any issues are quickly addressed.

By implementing this comprehensive backup strategy, the project ensures data is fully protected and can be swiftly recovered in case of any incident.

5.2.3 Additional security

For this project, while the primary data being collected is ecological and environmental (e.g., carbon and nitrogen inputs, food web structures, hydrology), there may still be a need for additional security measures to protect sensitive aspects of the research, such as the exact locations of protected wetlands or unpublished methodologies.

Potential Risks:

1. Data Integrity and Theft:

- o Unauthorized access or malicious intent could lead to data theft, manipulation, or corruption, especially in a collaborative setting with multiple users accessing shared data.

2. Sensitive Ecological Data:

- o The exact locations of sensitive or protected ecosystems (e.g., Ramsar sites, Natura 2000 areas) may need additional protection to prevent unwanted exploitation or harm to these areas.

3. Collaboration and Sharing Risks:

- o In cases where external collaborators are granted access, there may be risks associated with data sharing over unsecured networks or unauthorized distribution of research output before publication.

Security Measures:

1. Data Encryption:

- o All sensitive datasets, especially those involving geographical coordinates or specific environmental conditions of protected sites, will be encrypted both at rest and in transit using industry-standard encryption methods.

- o Files will be shared through secure file transfer protocols (SFTP) to ensure data is not intercepted or altered during transmission.

2. Access Control:

- o Access will be strictly limited to authorized personnel through role-based access controls (RBAC). Only designated researchers will have write/edit permissions, while other collaborators will be restricted to read-only access.

- o Multi-factor authentication (MFA) will be enforced to add an extra layer of protection when accessing sensitive data.

3. Data Anonymization:

- o If there is any risk of sensitive information exposure (e.g., exact locations of endangered species or vulnerable ecosystems), data anonymization techniques will be applied to remove specific identifying details from public datasets or shared files.

4. Regular Audits and Monitoring:

- o Continuous monitoring of data access logs will be in place to track who accesses, modifies, or downloads data, ensuring transparency and accountability.

- o Regular security audits will be conducted to identify vulnerabilities in the data management system and to ensure compliance with security protocols.

5. Incident Response Plan:

- o In case of a security breach or data leak, a response plan will be in place, including immediate measures such as revoking access, investigating the breach, and restoring data from secure backups.

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